

Substance Use as Correlates of Disruptive Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta State

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State, Nigeria. The study adopted the correlational research design. The study was guided by three research questions and three hypotheses. The population of the study comprise 40,959 Junior Secondary School (JSS) 3 students for the 2023/2024 academic session in Delta State. The sample size of the study comprises 1,056 students. Data was collected using a questionnaire, which was validated by expert judgment and factor analysis. The reliability of the instrument was confirmed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. It yielded the following coefficients Substance Use Rating Scale = 0.95; and Disruptive Behaviour Rating Scale = 0.93. The questionnaire was administered by the researcher and six research assistants. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. descriptive statistics was computed to answer research questions while inferential statistics of regression were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study that substance use and disruptive behaviour are low. There is a significant relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour. There was no significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour, but there was a significant moderating impact of school location in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State. Based on these findings, the study recommends that although substance use is low, counsellors should continue to provide educational programs about the risks and consequences of substance abuse.

Keywords: Substance Use; Disruptive Behaviour; Sex; School Location.

Introduction

Most secondary school students fall within the adolescent stage of human development, a period characterized by rapid physical growth, emotional volatility, and significant cognitive and social transitions. When these developmental changes are not properly guided, adolescents may exhibit maladaptive or deviant behaviours. One common manifestation of such maladjustment is disruptive behaviour.

Disruptive behaviour among adolescents refers to patterns of action that deviate from acceptable social norms and interfere with the harmonious functioning of individuals and institutions. It often involves defiance of authority, aggression, non-compliance with rules, and disregard for the well-being of others (Adewumi & Owoeye, 2021). Such behaviours can appear as verbal or physical aggression, persistent conflict with teachers or peers, disobedience, or actions that hinder the smooth functioning of social environments such as schools and homes.

Within the school setting, disruptive behaviour encompasses any conduct that obstructs the teaching-learning process or undermines classroom management. Examples include unnecessary talking, inattentiveness, noise-making, and engaging in side conversations during lessons. These behaviours are often associated with boredom, low engagement with schoolwork, or the desire for attention. Adolescents who disobey teachers or challenge authority may be expressing a sense of independence or reacting to conflicts within the family (Ogunleye & Alade, 2022). Others may habitually skip classes or arrive late, possibly due to personal problems, lack of motivation, or domestic instability. Family dysfunctions such as parental conflict, neglect, or poor communication often contribute to disruptive tendencies, as adolescents react to emotional tension and stress (Eze & Nwosu, 2023).

Studies show that disruptive behaviours are among the most frequently reported behavioural challenges in childhood and adolescence (Abdullahi & Bello, 2021). Globally, the prevalence of such behaviours has been estimated between 8% and 12% of school-aged populations (Olawale & Ojo, 2020). Behavioural problems of this nature have been described as one of the leading causes of academic failure, classroom disorder, and early school dropout (Oluwatosin, 2022). The occurrence of disruptive behaviour varies by social class, geographical location, and family background, suggesting that contextual factors influence its manifestation.

Although statistical data on the prevalence of disruptive behaviour in Nigeria remain limited, classroom observations in Delta State indicate that many secondary school students display these behaviours, which negatively affect both their academic achievement and that of their peers. This issue is of serious concern because such behaviours not only endanger the student but also disrupt school order and hinder effective teaching and learning. Common examples include bullying, substance use, violence, intimidation, and general disregard for authority. These actions consume teachers' instructional time and undermine the stability of the classroom (Afolabi & Adeyemi, 2021).

The impact of disruptive behaviour extends beyond the individual student. It can damage teacher-student relationships, increase teacher stress, and contribute to burnout (Usman & Ibrahim, 2023). Without appropriate intervention, disruptive behaviours that emerge

during adolescence tend to persist and may evolve into more serious antisocial behaviours such as aggression, delinquency, and criminality in adulthood (Adebayo, 2022). Such behavioural patterns pose long-term risks for emotional instability, substance abuse, and social maladjustment.

The negative consequences of disruptive behaviour are not confined to the school environment. They affect the wider society by fostering patterns of indiscipline, deviance, and social disorder. Adolescents who exhibit disruptive behaviour are at higher risk of engaging in substance use, truancy, and conflict with the law (Eze & Nwosu, 2023). They often experience poor academic performance and strained relationships with teachers and peers, which can extend into adulthood in the form of unemployment, depression, and criminal involvement (Olawale & Ojo, 2020). Consequently, disruptive behaviour constitutes a significant educational and public health concern.

Nkomo (2021) stressed that indiscipline among students in schools has become a pressing national issue, strongly linked to the level of moral decay and instability in many families. Parents and guardians, who serve as the primary agents of socialization, play a vital role in shaping children's behaviour. Hence, family structure, communication, and parenting style are crucial in determining whether a child will develop socially acceptable behaviours or deviant ones. Although numerous factors contribute to disruptive behaviour among secondary school students, this study specifically examines substance use as a correlate of disruptive behaviour among adolescents in secondary schools.

Substance use refers to the consumption of substances such as alcohol, tobacco, prescription drugs and illicit drugs by individuals. This behaviour among secondary school students involves the ingestion or use of these substances for various reasons, including recreational purposes, experimentation, self-medication, or as a response to peer pressure or social influences. Substance use can involve a range of substances, including alcohol, tobacco, marijuana, prescribed medications (when not prescribed by a medical professional), and illicit drugs like cocaine, methamphetamine, or opioids. Students may engage in substance use for various reasons, such as curiosity, stress relief, socializing, coping with academic pressures, or attempting to fit in with certain peer groups. Some students may use substances to self-medicate emotional or psychological issues, such as depression, anxiety, or trauma, as they may not have access to appropriate mental health support.

Substance use may likely influence disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in several ways. According to Jacobus et al. (2020), substance use, especially alcohol and drugs, can impair cognitive functions such as judgment, decision-making, and impulse control. When students are under the influence, they may be more likely to engage in disruptive behaviour without fully considering the consequences. According to Buddy (2020), substance use can lower inhibitions, making students more prone to engaging in disruptive and impulsive actions that they might not consider while sober. This can include speaking out of tune, acting aggressively, or defying school rules. Substance use is often associated with peer pressure. Students who use substances in a group setting may feel pressured to conform to disruptive behaviours initiated by their peers, further contributing to disruptions in the school environment. Some students turn to substances as a way to escape from personal problems or

cope with stress. The use of substances to deal with emotional challenges can lead to increased disruptive behaviour as a maladaptive response to underlying issues.

According to Fite, et al. (2018), substance use can lead to absenteeism, truancy, and a lack of engagement in school. When students skip classes or are frequently absent due to substance-related issues, it disrupts their educational progress and can lead to discipline problems. Substance use, particularly alcohol and certain drugs, can lead to heightened aggression and conflicts. Students under the influence may become more argumentative, confrontational, or even physically aggressive, disrupting the school environment and safety. Students engaged in substance use may form associations with peers who have similar behaviours, leading to a cycle of disruptive actions, negative influences, and a hostile school environment. Substance use can exacerbate underlying mental health issues, such as depression, anxiety, or conduct disorders. These conditions can contribute to disruptive behaviour (Martel, et al., 2019). Importantly, not all students who use substances engage in disruptive behaviour, and disruptive behaviour can have various causes.

The above discussion shows that indeed substance use may have ways of influencing disruptive behaviour among secondary school students. The researcher also believes that sex and school location could have some moderating impacts on the relationship. This is because both factors shape exposure, susceptibility, and response to behavioural risks. Sex influences how individuals experience and express the effects of substance use, as well as how they engage in disruptive behaviours. Research has shown that male students are generally more likely to engage in substance use and display externalising behaviours such as aggression, defiance, and delinquency, whereas female students tend to exhibit more internalising behaviours such as anxiety and depression (Adebayo & Olatunji, 2022). The social norms surrounding masculinity often encourage risk-taking and experimentation, which can increase the likelihood that substance use will translate into outward disruptive acts. Conversely, females who engage in substance use may face stronger social sanctions, leading them to conceal their behaviour or channel its effects in less overtly disruptive ways (Okonkwo & Eze, 2021). Therefore, sex may moderate this relationship by strengthening or weakening the link between substance use and disruptive behaviour depending on gendered behavioural expectations and coping patterns.

Furthermore, school location plays a crucial role in shaping students' access to substances, exposure to deviant peers, and the prevailing behavioural norms within the community. In urban schools, students may have easier access to drugs and alcohol due to proximity to markets, bars, and peer networks that normalise substance use (Olawale & Yusuf, 2023). Urban environments are often associated with higher levels of social exposure, peer pressure, and weakened community monitoring, which can heighten the risk of substance-induced disruptive behaviours such as truancy, bullying, and classroom aggression. On the other hand, students in rural schools may experience less accessibility to substances but may also face unique stressors such as poverty, limited recreational activities, and lack of psychosocial support, which can influence both substance use patterns and behavioural outcomes (Ogunleye & Adewale, 2022). Thus, the moderating effect of school location reflects how environmental context either amplifies or mitigates the behavioural consequences of substance use.

Taken together, sex and school location interact with psychosocial and contextual factors to shape how substance use manifests in disruptive behaviours. Males in urban schools, for instance, may exhibit the strongest link between substance use and disruptive behaviour due to greater social tolerance for deviance and easier access to substances. Meanwhile, females in rural areas might experience weaker associations, possibly because of stricter community norms and closer family monitoring. Therefore, understanding these moderating influences is essential for designing targeted intervention programs that account for gender and environmental contexts. Schools and policymakers must consider how these factors intersect to influence behaviour, ensuring that prevention and counselling strategies are sensitive to both sex-based differences and location-specific risks (Nwankwo & Uzochukwu, 2024).

In view of the above, the focus of this study is on how family discourse, substance use and family structure can relate to disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the level of substance use among secondary school students in Delta State?
2. What is the level of disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State?
3. What is the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State
2. There is no significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State
3. There is no significant moderating impact of school location in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State

Methods

This study adopted a correlational research design. The study involved a population of 140,959 JSS 3 students in Delta State, Nigeria in the 2023/2024 academic session. The study sample included 1,056 JSS 3 students in Delta State. The choice of 1,056 as a sample size was informed by the recommendation of Gill, et al. (2020), that a sample size of 1,056 is sufficient for a population of between 100,000 and 249,999 at a 95% confidence interval. The sample size was drawn from 12 out of the 25 local government areas across the state. Simple random and convenience sampling techniques were used to select the respondents. Four local

government areas were drawn from each of the three senatorial districts using a simple random sampling technique such that all the Local Government Areas in Delta State were written on a piece of paper, folded and poured on a container, thereafter, the researcher picked four pieces of paper, representing the four selected Local Government Areas. This was done for each of the three senatorial districts in Delta State until all 12 local government areas were selected (four for each senatorial district). After selecting the 12 Local Government Areas, the researcher selected four schools from each of the selected local government areas making a total of 48 schools. The sampling technique that was used at this stage is the simple random sampling technique as explained above. After selecting the 48 schools, the researcher used a convenience sampling technique to select 22 students from each of the 48 selected schools, making a total of 1,056 students. The choice of a convenience sampling technique is because the researcher used only students who were available and were willing to participate in the study (Oyibo & Oghounu, 2023).

A questionnaire was used in this study. It contains three sections. Section A contains the demographic data of respondents such as sex and school location Section B contains the Substance Use Rating Scale; and Section D contains the Disruptive Behaviour Rating Scale. The Substance Use Rating Scale was adapted from the Drug Use Questionnaire, developed by Aleke (2013). The instrument contains 21 items, designed to measure the extent of use of several drugs having three components namely Substance, Beverages and Narcotics. The items were, however, reduced from 21 to 17 items after validation. The scale was structured on a rating scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1). The Disruptive Behaviour Rating Scale was adapted from Disruptive Behaviour Scale for Adolescents (DISBA), developed by Karimy, et al. (2018). It contains 29 items designed in reference to the literature review and semi-structured interviews with students and high school authorities. The items cover four components namely Disruptive, Unruly, Troublesome and Destructive. The items were, however, reduced from 29 to 21 items after validation. The scale was structured on a rating scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1).

The research instrument was validated by experts' judgment and factor analysis. This is to ensure that the instruments met face, content and construct validities. The items were given to experts in Guidance and Counselling Department, who established the face validity of the instrument. Some of the items were corrected by the experts in terms of language choice, to suite the purpose of the study. Some of the experts suggested the removal of items that looked similar to other items. Some items were rephrased in terms of sentence structure Their opinions and recommendations were taken into consideration in drafting the final instruments. Factor analysis of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was used to establish the content and construct validities of the instruments. A total of 100 copies of the instrument was pilot-tested on junior secondary school students in Edo State, and the data obtained were subjected to factor analysis. The total cumulative variance was used to estimate the content validity of the instrument. It yielded the following values Substance Use Rating Scale = 69.46; and Disruptive Behaviour Rating Scale = 66.82%. The Rotated Component Matrix was used to estimate the construct validity of the instrument. It yielded the following range of values Substance Use Rating Scale = 0.59-0.89; and Disruptive Behaviour Rating Scale = 0.52-0.82. In order to ensure that the instrument is reliable, the data were subjected to Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient. It yielded the following coefficients Substance Use Rating Scale = 0.95; and Disruptive Behaviour Rating

Scale = 0.93. These figures indicates that the instrument is both valid and reliable (Jessa, et al., 2023).

The questionnaire was administered to the respondents by the researcher personally with the assistance of six research assistants. The researcher and assistants visited the various schools that were used for the study to administer the data. They sought and obtained the permission of the principals of the various schools. The instrument was retrieved immediately to avoid loss of data. At the end of the exercise, a total of 1,056 copies of questionnaire were administered and a total of 1,056 were retrieved, indicating 100% retrieval rate. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions 1 and 2 at 2.50 benchmark, Pearsons’s coefficient of determination was used to answer research question 3; regression statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (Version 26) was used for the analysis.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of substance use among secondary school students in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean analysis of the level of substance use among secondary school students in Delta State

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Ecstasy	2.30	1.17	Low
2	Tobacco (snuff)	2.27	1.16	Low
3	Lipton	2.25	1.12	Low
4	Alcohol (beer, palm wine, burukutu, kai-kai, ogoro, gin, whisky)	2.11	1.16	Low
5	tranquillizers (sleeping pills like valium)	2.05	1.21	Low
6	Ketamine	2.04	1.18	Low
7	Cigarette	1.88	1.09	Low
8	LSD/Acid	1.85	1.03	Low
9	Amphetamine (uppers, pep pills, bennies, speed)	1.84	1.05	Low
10	Coffee	1.84	1.01	Low
11	Cocaine	1.80	1.00	Low
12	Bitter kola	1.75	1.08	Low
13	Barbiturate (secobarbital, Phenobarbital, “red devils”)	1.75	0.97	Low
14	Marijuana (Indian hemp, ganja, grass or igbo)	1.75	1.09	Low
15	Caffeine	1.74	0.90	Low
16	Heroin (igbana, smack, horse)	1.71	0.98	Low
17	Cola nut	1.67	0.91	Low
Average Mean		1.92	1.07	Low

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 1 presents a detailed analysis of the mean scores related to the level of substance use among secondary school students in Delta State. The findings indicate that the mean scores for family discourse range from 1.67 to 2.30, with an overall average mean of 1.92. Given that the criterion mean is set at 2.50, these results suggest that the level of substance use among secondary school students in Delta State is low.

Research Question 2: What is the level of disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State?

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Table 2: Mean analysis of the level of disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	I get expelled from class due to inappropriate behaviour	2.13	1.12	Low
2	I sometimes come to school after taking drugs	1.96	1.02	Low
3	I clash with teachers	1.95	1.02	Low
4	I argue with my classmates	1.94	1.14	Low
5	I sing out loud at school	1.93	0.96	Low
6	I hit the school trees	1.92	1.15	Low
7	I cannot relate well with my friends	1.92	1.00	Low
8	I do not pay attention to the lessons in the classroom	1.87	1.03	Low
9	I like to disrupt the class	1.82	0.99	Low
10	I love to carve on the school benches	1.81	1.02	Low
11	I break the branches of the school trees	1.81	1.06	Low
12	I forget to bring the things I need to school	1.79	1.05	Low
13	I deliberately break or damage school equipment	1.79	1.04	Low
14	I argue with teachers	1.77	0.91	Low
15	I leave my seat without teacher's permission	1.70	0.96	Low
16	I stick gum on the seats	1.69	0.91	Low
17	I eat in class without permission	1.69	0.96	Low
18	I speak without permission	1.67	0.94	Low
19	I text messages in class while the teacher is teaching	1.63	0.97	Low
20	I do not stand up when the teacher enters the class	1.58	0.91	Low
21	I do not turn up on time for school	1.57	0.87	Low
Average Mean		1.81	1.00	Low

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 2 presents a detailed analysis of the mean scores related to the level of disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State. The findings indicate that the mean scores for family discourse range from 1.57 to 2.13, with an overall average mean of 1.81. Given that the criterion mean is set at 2.50, these results suggest that the level of disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State is low.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State?

Table 3: Correlation and coefficient of determination of the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State

Variable	<i>n</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i> ²	<i>r</i> ² %	Decision
Substance Use					
Disruptive Behaviour	1,056	0.558	0.311	31.1	Positive Relationship

Table 3 revealed an r-value of 0.558, which indicated the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State. The result revealed a positive relationship between the two variables. Substance use contributed 31.1% to the variability in disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State

Table 4: Regression analysis of the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	58611.854	1	58611.854	471.135	.000 ^b
Residual	129630.724	1042	124.406		
Total	188242.578	1043			

Variables in Equation					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standardised Coefficient	t	Sig	
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	18.639	.936		19.917	.000
Substance Use	.596	.027	.558	21.706	.000

$\alpha = 0.05, R = 0.558, R\text{-Square} = 0.311$

a. **Dependent Variable:** Disruptive Behaviour

b. **Predictors (Constant):** Substance Use

Table 4 shows a regression analysis of the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State. The result shows that $F(1, 1042) = 471.135, p < 0.05$ level of significance. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State. The R^2 value of 0.311 showed that 31.1% of the variance in disruptive behaviour was accounted for by substance use. The unstandardized coefficient (B) for predicting disruptive behaviour from substance use is 0.596; the standardized coefficient (β) from substance use is 0.558, $t = 21.706$. Substance use is significant at an alpha level of 0.05.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State

Table 5: Multiple regression analysis on moderating impact of sex in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State

Model	B	Std Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	17.762	1.443		12.307	.000
Substance Use	.597	.028	.559	21.703	.000
Sex	.553	.692	.021	.799	.425

Table 5 shows the result of the moderating impact of sex in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State. The beta weights of 0.559, $t = 21.703$ for substance use; and 0.021, $t = 0.799$ for sex are indicators of the degree of correlation between each variable of substance use and sex with disruptive behaviour. From the result, substance use is significant at an alpha level of 0.05, but sex is not significant. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that there is no significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State.

Hypothesis 6: There is no significant moderating impact of school location in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State

Table 6: Multiple regression analysis on moderating impact of school location in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State

Model	B	Std Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	21.863	1.624		13.467	.000
Substance Use	.587	.030	.550	19.673	.000
School Location	-1.913	.754	-.071	-2.539	.011

Table 6 shows the result of the moderating impact of school location in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State. The beta weights of 0.550, $t = 19.673$ for substance use; and -0.071, $t = -2.539$ for school location are indicators of the degree of correlation between each variable of substance use and school location with disruptive behaviour. From the result, substance use and school location are significant at an alpha level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that there is a significant moderating impact of school location in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State.

Discussions

The first finding showed that the level of substance use among secondary school students in Delta State is low. This finding suggests that substance abuse is not as prevalent among this population as might be expected. Several factors could contribute to this outcome. First, increased awareness and education about the dangers of substance use could play a significant role. Schools and communities may have implemented effective drug education programs that emphasize the risks associated with substance use, leading to greater resistance among students. Additionally, strong family and community ties could be a protective factor, as students who have supportive relationships at home and within their communities are less likely to engage in risky behaviours, including substance use. Cultural and religious influences might also be significant in this context. Delta State, like many other regions in Nigeria, has a strong cultural and religious presence that often discourages behaviours deemed harmful or immoral, such as substance abuse. This cultural backdrop could contribute to a lower incidence of substance use among secondary school students. This finding agrees with Azuike et al. (2021), who found that comprehensive drug education programs and active community participation in Delta State schools have led to a significant reduction in substance use among students. These programs often involve collaborations between schools, parents, and local organizations, which help reinforce anti-drug messages and provide students with the necessary support to avoid substance use. The finding is however, at variance with Eze et al. (2020), who noted that the stigma associated with substance use in many Nigerian communities can lead students to conceal their behaviours, resulting in lower prevalence rates in surveys. This indicates that while the level of substance use may appear low, there could be a hidden

prevalence that is not fully captured due to social desirability bias or fear of negative consequences.

The second finding revealed that the level of disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State is low. This finding suggests that students are generally well-behaved and adhere to school rules and expectations. Several factors could contribute to this outcome. One significant reason could be the implementation of effective disciplinary policies and behaviour management strategies within schools. Schools in Delta State may have established clear guidelines and consequences for disruptive behaviour, which could deter students from engaging in such actions. Additionally, teachers and school administrators might be more vigilant and proactive in addressing behavioural issues, creating an environment where disruptive behaviour is less likely to occur. Another contributing factor could be the influence of cultural and community values that emphasize respect for authority and elders. In many Nigerian communities, there is a strong emphasis on discipline and respect, which could extend into the school environment and influence students' behaviour. Furthermore, the role of parental involvement cannot be overlooked. Parents who are actively engaged in their children's education and behaviour tend to reinforce positive behaviour at home, which can translate into better conduct at school. This finding is in line with Oludayo and Olajide (2022), who found that schools with well-enforced behaviour management strategies and active parental involvement reported lower levels of disruptive behaviour among students. This suggests that a structured and supportive environment, both at home and in school, plays a crucial role in maintaining discipline among students. The finding however, disagrees with Eke and Ugwuegbu (2021), who noted that in some Nigerian schools, teachers might underreport incidents of disruptive behaviour either due to a lack of comprehensive reporting systems or to present a more favourable image of their school. This could result in artificially low rates of reported disruptive behaviour, making it seem that students are better behaved than they actually are.

The third finding showed that there is a significant relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State. This finding highlights a crucial concern in adolescent development. Substance use, particularly during adolescence, has been consistently linked to a range of behavioural issues, including disruptive behaviour. This relationship can be attributed to the psychoactive effects of substances, which often impair judgment, reduce self-control, and increase impulsivity. Adolescents who engage in substance use may struggle with following school rules, respecting authority, and maintaining healthy peer relationships, all of which can contribute to disruptive behaviour in the school setting. The reasons behind this significant relationship in Delta State may include socio-economic factors, peer pressure, and the availability of substances. Adolescents in regions with limited economic opportunities might turn to substance use as a coping mechanism for stress or to fit in with peers. Additionally, the prevalence of substance availability in certain communities may make it easier for students to access drugs, thereby increasing the likelihood of substance use and the associated behavioural issues. This finding agrees with Chan et al. (2020), who found that adolescents who engage in substance use are more likely to exhibit disruptive behaviours, including increased aggression and defiance, which are directly linked to the psychoactive effects of drugs on impulse control and emotional regulation. The finding also supports Marshall, et al. (2021), who reported that substance use significantly contributes to behavioural issues in school settings, highlighting the role of

substances in exacerbating risk-taking and non-compliance among adolescents. The study however, disagrees with Kim and Oesterle (2022), who found that while substance use is a strong predictor of disruptive behaviour, the impact may be lessened in environments where students receive strong emotional support from family and school, suggesting that the context can influence the severity of behavioural outcomes associated with substance use.

The fourth finding revealed that there is no significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State. This finding suggests that the effects of substance use on disruptive behaviour are consistent across both male and female students. This implies that substance use leads to disruptive behaviours irrespective of the student's sex, challenging some traditional views that boys and girls might respond differently to substance use due to gender-specific socialization processes. One reason for the above finding could be that the psychoactive effects of substances, such as impaired judgment and increased impulsivity, impact both male and female adolescents similarly. Regardless of sex, substance use can lead to similar patterns of behaviour, including aggression, rule-breaking, and defiance, due to the direct effects of drugs on cognitive and emotional regulation. Additionally, the broader social and environmental factors influencing behaviour, such as peer pressure and school context, might affect both genders equally, thereby diminishing any differential impact based on sex. This finding is in line with Nolen-Hoeksema and Hilt (2021), who found that the negative impacts of substance use, including increased disruptive behaviour, are consistent across genders. Their research showed that substance use leads to similar patterns of impulsivity and aggression in both boys and girls, suggesting that the effects are not significantly moderated by sex. The finding also agrees with Lanza and Rhoades (2020), who found that the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour did not vary significantly between males and females. They reported that the psychoactive effects of drugs, such as impaired self-control and increased risk-taking, led to disruptive behaviours across both sexes, highlighting that gender does not significantly alter the relationship between substance use and behaviour. The finding is however, at variance with Hawkins, et al. (2018), who found that boys were more likely to exhibit externalizing behaviours, such as aggression and rule-breaking, as a result of substance use, while girls might show different behavioural patterns. However, these findings might reflect earlier societal norms and changing trends in substance use and behaviour among adolescents.

The sixth finding showed that there is a significant moderating impact of school location in the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour among secondary school students in Delta State. This finding highlights the important role that the environment plays in shaping how substance use impacts student behaviour. This suggests that the effects of substance use on disruptive behaviour are not uniform but vary depending on whether the school is located in an urban or rural area. One reason for the above finding could be that schools in different locations face varying levels of social and environmental stressors that influence student behaviour. For example, students in urban schools may be exposed to higher levels of social and economic challenges, such as higher crime rates, greater peer pressure, and more prevalent substance use within the community. These factors can exacerbate the negative impacts of substance use, leading to more pronounced disruptive behaviours. On the other hand, rural schools may have a more cohesive community environment and fewer external stressors, which could moderate the impact of substance use on disruptive behaviour. Additionally, the availability of school resources and support systems can differ significantly

between urban and rural areas. Urban schools may have more access to counselling services and behavioural interventions, which can help mitigate the effects of substance use on behaviour. In contrast, rural schools might have limited resources, making students more vulnerable to the negative consequences of substance use. This finding agrees with Osgood, et al. (2022), who found that urban schools, with higher levels of social and economic stress, experience more pronounced effects of substance use on disruptive behaviour compared to rural schools. They noted that urban environments often have higher levels of peer pressure and exposure to substance use, which can amplify the negative behavioural outcomes associated with substance use. The finding is also in line with Chen and O'Brien (2021), who demonstrated that the impact of substance use on behaviour is moderated by the school location, with urban students exhibiting greater levels of disruptive behaviour as a result of substance use compared to their rural counterparts. This finding was attributed to the differences in community resources and support systems available in urban versus rural areas, which influence how substance use affects student behaviour. The finding however, disagrees with Durlak and DuPre (2019), who found that while school environment factors do play a role, the overall effect of substance use on disruptive behaviour did not significantly vary by school location. This discrepancy might be due to different methodological approaches or the focus on broader factors rather than specific contextual elements like school location.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that there is a generally positive behavioural environment among secondary school students in Delta State. Despite various factors that could potentially influence student behaviour, such as substance use, the levels of disruptive behaviour remain relatively low. This indicates that the existing conditions and interventions may be effective in mitigating potential behavioural issues. The lack of significant gender differences in how substance use impact disruptive behaviour points to a universal pattern in these relationships, suggesting that the mechanisms underlying disruptive behaviour are similar across genders. This uniformity can simplify the approach to managing and addressing behavioural issues, as interventions do not need to be tailored differently for boys and girls. On the other hand, the influence of school location on the relationship between substance use and disruptive behaviour indicates that the contextual factors associated with urban versus rural settings play a crucial role. This suggests that school-specific factors, including the social and economic environment, are important considerations when developing strategies to address student behaviour. In view of this, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Although substance use is low, counsellors should continue to provide educational programs about the risks and consequences of substance abuse.
- ii. Counsellors should implement targeted interventions that address both substance use and behavioural issues.
- iii. Counsellors should develop substance abuse prevention and intervention programs that are equally effective for all students, regardless of sex.
- iv. Counsellors should adapt their approaches based on the school's location, as urban and rural environments may influence how substance use affects behaviour.

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